

Reference List for the Entry: 'Diffusionsmodellanalysen [Diffusion Model Analyses]'

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Date: June 13, 2025

This document contains the full reference list from the encyclopedia entry “Röhner, J., & Schütz, A. (2021). Diffusionsmodellanalysen. In M. Wirtz (Hrsg.), *Dorsch – Lexikon der Psychologie* (20. überarb. Aufl., S. 443). Hogrefe.” The original text is not included for copyright reasons. The reference list is provided here separately to help researchers find the cited works more easily.

References

1. Röhner, J. & Ewers, T. (2016). Trying to separate the wheat from the chaff: Construct- and faking-related variance on the Implicit Association Test (IAT). *Behavior Research Methods*, 48, 243-258. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13428-015-0568-1>
2. Röhner, J. & Thoss, P. J. (2018). EZ: An Easy Way to Conduct a More Fine-Grained Analysis of Faked and Nonfaked Implicit Association Test (IAT) Data. *The Quantitative Methods for Psychology*, 14, 17–35. 10.20982/tqmp.14.1.p017
3. Voss, A., Rothermund, K., Gast, A. & Wentura, D. (2013). Cognitive processes in categorical and associative priming: A diffusion model analysis. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, 142, 536–559. 10.1037/a0029459